

The Plight of Indian Women in Chithra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Bats and Clothes*

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Masimalar, S. "The Plight of Indian Women in Chithra Banerjee Divakaruni's Short Stories, *The Bats and Clothes*." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 25–28.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3461747>

S. Masimalar

*Assistant Professor, Department of English
P.M.Thevar College, Usilampatti*

Abstract

*This paper focuses on Divakaruni's depiction of women characters in the selected short stories in the book *Arranged Marriage* (1995). The stories taken into account are *The Bats and Clothes*. Divakaruni deals with a variety of themes related to women. These include arranged marriages, domestic violence, bride viewing, longing to become parents, responsibility of educated women, burden of an extended family, life abroad and many more. The women characters of Divakaruni are very varied. The protagonists of Divakaruni are sometimes educated and sometimes illiterate; sometimes assertive and sometimes very submissive.*

Keywords: Exploitation, Restriction, Autonomous, Domestic Violence.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni is one of the female writers. She depicts through her works, the condition of women in the society. Divakaruni was born in Kolkatta in India in the year 1956. Currently she lives in Texas and she is a co-founder and former president of Maitri, a helpline founded in 1991 for South Asian Women dealing with domestic abuse. She has written numerous short stories, novels, and poetry. Her first collection of short stories *Arranged Marriage* won an American Book Award, a PEN Josephine Miles Award, and a Bay Area Book Reviewer's Award. *Arranged Marriage* is a collection of eleven stories, which are diverse in theme, characters and narration, yet bound together by the common thread of marriage.

Men become self-proclaimed protectors of women in the form of father, brother, husband and son. And then began the exploitation. Women have been exploited and ill-treated by their own protectors throughout the world. In every society of the world, women have been considered secondary in position. They have been made to live under severe restrictions. Their lives have never been theirs. Women in the Indian society are forced by men to accept the status of an inferior. In order to gain equality and to realize their human potential, women must become autonomous. They must take their position strong in society by attaining education and at the same time they must raise their voice against any kind of exploitation.

The first story in the book *Arranged Marriage* is "The Bats". The story is an account of a married woman who constantly suffers

beating at the hands of her husband but never fights back. The beating is disclosed to us by the narrator and the daughter of the woman. The daughter comes to know of the beating that her mother is suffered through the “yellow blotch with its edges turning purple” (2) and through another mark on her face “even bigger and reddish-blue” (3). The heart rending depiction of the plight that is presented by Divakaruni in “The Bats” leaves the readers gasping for breath. The first sentence of the story tells the whole story: “That year Mother cried a lot nights. Or maybe she had always cried, and that was the first year I was old enough to notice” (1).

Wife- beating has been a very rampant practice in the world and India is no exception. Many men show their valour through this practice as if beating a woman makes them more manly.

The mother does take a brave step and leaves, while the husband is asleep, along with the daughter to one of her uncle’s house. The uncle’s place is very tiny, “almost a play house, with mud walls and straw on the roof like in my storybook pictures”(6). The life for the narrator there is very eventful and joyful. She doesn’t like to see the mother crying night after night and no bruises anymore. But the compulsion of the societal norms are so strong that the mother is compelled to inform by herself their whereabouts to the husband. The husband commits not to repeat the torture and urges them to come back home. The joyful life of the narrator comes to an end abruptly and she is back to her father’s home in no time. But the mother faces the same fate. The mother and the daughter have to leave like this many times but always they have to come back.

The comparison with the ‘bats’ is indeed very appealing. The bats keep coming back to spoil the mangoes. Grandpa-Uncle tries everything “sticks and drums and magic powder from the wise woman in the next village” (8), but nothing seems to work. Finally, grandpa-uncle has to use poison. What are the compulsions that make bats keep coming back to the mango orchard? Even after being poisoned, some of them keep coming. The mother and the daughter are beaten day after day. They leave the house; but come back again. The compulsion in this case is the society that does not allow a woman to live away from her husband. The woman has to adjust her husband. If she revolts, she is immortal.

The second story, “Clothes”, is basically about the unfilled promises of the marital bond. Sumita has a number of dreams, just like any other young girl would have. The dream that her handsome prince: “would take her to his kingdom beyond the seven seas” (18). Somesh Sen, her would be husband, lives in the US and she will have to go with her husband after marriage because, “a married woman belongs to her husband, her in-laws” (19). Somesh is a kind husband and encourages Sumitha to get a degree in teaching. Sumita is gratified with the fact that Somesh has such confidence in her. She dreams and pictures herself “in front of a classroom of girls with blond pigtails and blue uniforms, like a scene out of an English movie”(27). But her dreams are shattered when Somesh is killed by a burglar in his store ‘7-Eleven’. So the promises of the marital bond are not fulfilled by the turn of events.

Another very profound theme that has been highlighted in “Clothes” is of bride-viewing. Bride-viewing is a very common practice in India. Girls wear beautiful clothes, put on the make-up, and get ready to be viewed by the prospective groom. The boy comes, the girl comes with tea in the tray, the boy and the in-laws watch the girl- the way she walks, the way she has dressed up, her looks, her complexion, sometimes she is even asked to sing for the prospective groom and his family. People do not really realize the plight of the girl while she is viewed and assessed for whether she is worthy of the boy or not.

Sumita is also viewed by Somesh and his parents. She is made to wear the most beautiful sari for the day. She is prepared for viewing by her friends.

I close my eyes and smell the sweet brown odor of the ritha pulp my friends Deepali and Radha are working into my hair so it will glisten with little lights this evening. The scrub with more vigor

than usual and wash it out more carefully, because today is a special day. It is the day of my bride-viewing. (17)

Sumita is lucky enough to be chosen in the very first go. Radha, on the other hand, not that lucky. Her parents are also trying to arrange a marriage for her. “So far three families have come to see her, but no one chosen her because her skin colour is considered too dark”(19). This is a kind of materialization of women. They are seen as if they are some products the features of which are assessed and then decided whether to buy the product or not. This is the sad predicament of girls in the society depicted by Divakaruni in the story “Clothes”.

Sumita is a brave woman who cannot be mowed down by even most adverse circumstances. Her dreams have been shattered. The promises that came along with the marital bonding have been left unfulfilled. She is in a “dangerous land” (33), far away from her family. She has lost her very ‘loving’ and ‘caring’ husband and has been left all alone. But this does not make her, like many other widows, dead. She is not ready to be one of those widows” in white saris... bowing their veiled heads, serving tea to in-laws. Doves with cutoff wings”(33). She still has vigour for life left in her. She is not ready to yield to circumstances and is determined to start the life afresh though she is aware of the approaching remonstrations. “I straighten my shoulders and stand taller, take a deep breath. Air fills me – the same air that travelled through Somesh’s lungs a little while ago” (33).

The female characters of Divakaruni are very varied. The imperfect lives of these characters are depicted in the book *Arranged Marriage*. The women of Divakaruni are both liberated and trapped in their struggle to create their own identity as they are under the influence of cultural changes. The women are, many a times, Indian-born US-settled, who try to strike a balance between their hereditary cultural values and modern liberal thoughts. The challenges based by these women no different from what is talked about by other female writers-domestic violence, wife-beating, bride-viewing, exploitation, etc. Some women are educated and some are not educated. But the predicament of all the women, irrespective of their educational qualifications, is the same. They are supposed to rear children and take care of the household chores. Though not every husband is bad and not all in-laws are cruel but yet women have to go through a lot of adjustments in order to make the husband and the in-laws happy. The wives might not be consulted for the decisions taken by their male counterparts but of course the decisions taken by the women must be in consultation with the husbands. Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni writes: “Women in particular respond to my work because I am writing about them, women in love, in difficulties, women in relationships. I want people tolerated to my characters, to feel their joy and pain, because it will be harder to be prejudice when they meet them in real life” (qtd. in Chaturvedi 55)

Divakaruni’s female characters are rebellious and bold. They are in a pursuit of self-realization though they are absolutely aware of the potential remonstrations. They, many a times, go against the conventions of the society to register their protest. The conventions formed by the male – chauvinistic society. Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni also, very vividly, puts forth the fact that whether women are educated or not; whether they belong to rich families or not; whether they go for arranged marriages or not, their fate is almost the same in the patriarchal world. They will have to fight their battles themselves and will have to get through their battles themselves and will have to get through their trials and tribulations on their own. C.J.Wallia comments: “Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni’s book of short stories, *Arranged Marriage*, focuses on family-marriage matches, a century old tradition in India. These stories about Indian immigrants to the U.S show how the dislocation of immigration are making this tradition problematic” (7). Philipa Kafka credits Divakaruni as one of the diasporic

authors who “write eloquently on the issues that arise either for them or for their characters in the west” (26), and also Divakaruni writes with “Obvious compassion and full understanding of Indian women who go west” (Kafka 26).

Works Cited

1. Chaturvedi, Lata. “The Enigma of Female Bonding in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni’s “Queen of Dream.” *The Commonwealth Review*. 17.2: 55-56. Print.
2. Divakaruni, Chitra Banerjee. *Arranged Marriage*. London: Black Swan Book, 1997. Print.
3. Kafka, Phillipa. *On the Outside Looking Indian: Indian Women Writers at the Home and Abroad*. New York: Peter Lang. 2003. 26. Print.
4. Wallia, C.J. “A Cross Cultural Understanding Speed. With the Indian Diaspora@ Black issue.” By *Softly Elizabeth*. Web. 8 July 2010.